

Model for Maintaining Stability in Budget Allocation in Metropolitan Infrastructure Development Projects Using Cost-Risk Contingency

Syed Maqsood Zia, Imran Ahmed Shah*, Sirajud Din, Mansoor Ahmed Junejo, Mumtaz Ali Junejo, Fawwad Mahmood Butt, Saaherah Basil Alkilany, Ghulam Akbar Khaskheli

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Abstract

Risk analysis plays a vital role in controlling and managing cost overruns in complex construction projects, particularly where uncertainty is high. Numerous tools and techniques have been employed to better evaluate the risk and maintain stability in cost, but progress has been limited. In order to prevent cost overruns in metropolitan infrastructure development projects and assist decision makers ineffective budgeting for the future, a cost-risk contingency model has been developed using fuzzy logic and analytical hierarchy. A hierarchical structure to break down the risk in important risk factors has been designed using a relative importance index. The proposed cost-risk contingency model investigates the expected additional budget required to mitigate the consequences of the risks for particular project activities. To demonstrate the application of the proposed method for cost-risk analysis, metropolitan transit construction project for building a 25 km long track above the ground and 2 km long underground track is discussed. The results imply that poor design decisions, increase in material prices and delays in the relocation of facilities increase the risk of cost overrun in complex projects. The study describes a practical approach to address the common issue of project cost overrun problems in developing countries. This study contributes to the body of knowledge by providing a practical contingency model to identify and evaluate the additional risk cost required to calculate the total construction cost contributing to realistic and stable future budgets.

Introduction

The complex and dynamic nature of construction projects has led to a series of cost overrun issues over the years (Islam et al., 2017). Cost overrun issues in metropolitan mega-projects usually have an adverse impact on an economy, particularly in developing countries where the economy cannot support the additional cost incurred (Fang & Marle, 2012). It is worth mentioning that in the global construction sector nearly 86% of projects have experienced an overrun in cost compared to their initial forecasted costs. This is especially common in Asian emerging economies due to their dynamic market structure, limited resources and poor expertise level (Lind & Brunen, 2015; Liu et al., 2016). (Flyvbjerg et al., 2004) have conducted a study to find the major causes of cost escalation in transport projects. They concluded that projects like tunnel and bridge constructions exhibit large percentages of cost overruns over the project life cycle due to delays in process tasks, policy implications, and long implementation phases. Lee (Lee, 2008) has described the causes of cost overrun in Korean mega capital projects. The results of his study show that 95 to 100% of transport construction projects are likely to have a cost overrun of more than 50% of the initial estimate. (Afzal et al., 2018) have documented that almost 76% of large construction projects in Asia have cost underestimation problems. Because of the rapid growth in infrastructure projects in developing economies (Ou-Yang & Chen, 2017), the focus of capital investments has shifted towards high-tech transit projects and mass rapid transit projects (Masrom et al., 2015). Almost all of these projects are experiencing cost overruns problems because of limited resources and low expertise levels available (Fang & Marle, 2012). In these projects, multiple stakeholders are involved: clients, contractors, consultants, domestic and foreign financial institutions, suppliers, local government and so on (Xia et al., 2018) which is a major concern for the progress of the project. Effective construction management requires a timely realization of the project tasks in accordance with the desires of all aforementioned key stakeholders (Afzal et al., 2018). Therefore, effective cost risk analysis in developing countries is essential to identify potential causes of cost overruns and to achieve effective cost planning (Islam & Nepal, 2016; Khodakarami & Abdi, 2014; Love et al., 2016). Lack of skills and experience in cost analysis can lead to major cost overruns and termination of the project prior to completion (Samantra et al., 2017). In order to ensure the success of a project,

a proactive framework is required to address uncertainties, to manage inherent risks of cost overruns, especially for metropolitan construction, and to develop a contingency plan.

Developing an appropriate cost-risk contingency model for cost overrun has been a challenge for many years, and different approaches have been adopted to better analyze the impact of risk factors on cost overrun in infrastructure construction projects (Fan & Yu, 2004; Kardes et al., 2013; Valipour et al., 2015). A growing complexity in project activities raises the uncertainty and increases the risk factors which effect the project cost (Fang et al., 2013). In order to explore these complexity-driven risk factors, previous studies elucidated the project risks associated with cost overruns in complex construction projects (Afzal et al., 2018; Hastak & Shaked, 2000; Samantra et al., 2017; Valipour et al., 2016). Hastak and Shaked (Hastak & Shaked, 2000) have presented an international construction risk assessment model containing 73 risk factors divided into three categories (i.e., macro level, market level, and project level). More recently, (Samantra et al., 2017), (Qazi et al., 2016), and Love et al. (Love et al., 2016) have evaluated complexity-driven risks addressing cost overrun issues in international construction projects.

In order to ensure the successful project outcomes in metropolitan infrastructure projects in developing countries, initially, a unique structured hierarchy of complexity-driven cost-risk factors has been developed using an anonymous database of focus group study results. The hierarchical breakdown structure comprises of critical risk factors across different endogenous and exogenous project risk dimensions (Dikmen et al., 2007; Samantra et al., 2017). Subsequently, a cost-risk contingency model for managing cost overruns in metropolitan transit projects is proposed. A cost analysis of an empirical case is performed for validating the model and for evaluating the sensitivity of the cost for certain risk factors. This cost-risk contingency model not only addresses the impact of risk on specific project cost but also explains the tentative risk cost required in order to estimate the total construction cost and maintain stability in future budgeting. In doing so, cost-risk analysis is an important aspect of cost estimation that helps industry experts to understand not only the potential causes of cost overruns but also the unpredictability of cost behavior and possible responses to them (Shah et al., 2020).

Preliminaries of cost-risk contingency frameworks are presented in Section 2. Section 3 explains the procedural steps taken to develop a cost-risk contingency framework. For cost analysis, an empirical case application of a metropolitan transit project is described in Section 4. Key findings and discussions are presented in section 5. Finally, conclusions and limitations of the study as well as possible future studies are described in Section 6.

Cost-Risk Contingency Modeling

A number of studies have been found in the literature describing hybrid methods in measuring the impact of risk on project cost under high uncertainty (Islam et al., 2017; Kabir et al., 2016; Sadeghi et al., 2010; Shafiee, 2015; Yazdi & Kabir, 2017). The use of fuzzy hybrid methods such as Fuzzy Analytical Network Processing (Shafiee, 2015), Fuzzy Bayesian Belief Networks (Kabir et al., 2016), Fuzzy Neural Networks (Chan et al., 2009) and Fuzzy Monte Carlo Simulation (Ou-Yang & Chen, 2017; Sadeghi et al., 2010; Salling & Leleur, 2015) appear to be superior to multi-criteria decision models (Hastak & Shaked, 2000; Li et al., 2013; Shariat et al., 2019; Valipour et al., 2015) for risk analysis. Among these methods, the Fuzzy Monte Carlo Simulation approach is popular for project risk re-evaluation (Shariat et al., 2019) and cost analysis (Choudhry et al., 2014) as it gives the most realistic results after multiple iterations of specific scenarios (Terstegen et al., 2016). This study has utilized an integrated approach of Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy-AHP) for risk prioritization and simulates results for cost-risk re-evaluation process under high level of project uncertainty.

Fuzzy Set Theory

A well-recognized decision tool for uncertainty measurement, called fuzzy logic, assesses the vulnerability of the risk events based on the subjective evaluation. Fuzziness is a transformation process of an element in a set of non-membership and membership states (Kabir et al., 2016). However, the basic limitation of fuzzy models is that they do not consider complex risk interactions (Jin, 2010; Karimiazari et al., 2011). Therefore, the Fuzzy-AHP method has been utilized herein for addressing important risk interactions and ranking of key cost-risk factors.

In this study, a generalized trapezoidal fuzzy membership function (Prascevic & Prascevic, 2017) has been adopted to describe the likelihood of occurrence and consequences of a risk event. A generalized trapezoidal fuzzy membership function (Prascevic & Prascevic, 2017) has been defined as: a fuzzy function $\tilde{F} = (b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4; \omega)$, belonging to the real field R . It defines a membership function: $\delta_{\tilde{A}}(Z): \rightarrow [0, n], z \in R$. This membership function $\delta_{\tilde{A}}(Z)$ is articulated as:

$$\delta_{\tilde{F}}(Z) = \begin{cases} 0, & y < 0 \\ \frac{y - b_1}{b_2 - b_1} \omega, & b_1 \leq y < b_2 \\ \omega, & b_2 \leq y \leq b_3 \\ \frac{b_4 - y}{b_4 - b_1} \omega, & b_3 < y \leq b_4 \\ 0, & y > 0 \end{cases}$$

$b_1 \leq b_2 \leq b_3 \leq b_4$, and $y \leq b_3$ is the cross over distribution interval in \tilde{F} . The weight ω belongs to the maximum height of $\delta_{\tilde{F}}(Z)$. Two trapezoidal fuzzy membership functions for likelihood and impact are expressed as:

$$\tilde{F}_1 = (b_{1i}, b_{2i}, b_{3i}, b_{4i}; \omega_{1i}) \text{ and } \tilde{F}_2 = (b_{5i}, b_{6i}, b_{7i}, b_{8i}; \omega_{2i})$$

Where, the \tilde{F}_1 function expresses the likelihood of the occurrence vector and the \tilde{F}_2 function expresses the magnitude of the impact vector of an event. For pair-wise comparison in AHP, the reciprocals of the trapezoidal fuzzy membership functions are expressed as:

$$\tilde{F}_1^{-1} = (b_{1i}, b_{2i}, b_{3i}, b_{4i}; \omega_{1i})^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{b_{1i}}, \frac{1}{b_{2i}}, \frac{1}{b_{3i}}, \frac{1}{b_{4i}}; \omega_{1i} \right) \tag{2}$$

$$\tilde{F}_2^{-1} = (b_{5i}, b_{6i}, b_{7i}, b_{8i}; \omega_{2i})^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{b_{5i}}, \frac{1}{b_{6i}}, \frac{1}{b_{7i}}, \frac{1}{b_{8i}}; \omega_{2i} \right) \tag{3}$$

The algorithms for addition and multiplication of the membership functions are described as follows:
When two fuzzy numbers are added:

$$\tilde{F}_{1i} \oplus \tilde{F}_{2i} = (b_{1i} + b_{5i}, b_{2i} + b_{6i}, b_{3i} + b_{7i}, b_{4i} + b_{8i}; \omega_{1i} = \min\{\omega_{1i}, \omega_{2i}\}) \tag{4}$$

When two fuzzy functions are multiplied:

$$\tilde{F}_{1i} \otimes \tilde{F}_{2i} = (b_{1i} \times b_{5i}, b_{2i} \times b_{6i}, b_{3i} \times b_{7i}, b_{4i} \times b_{8i}; \omega_{1i} = \min\{\omega_{1i}, \omega_{2i}\}) \tag{5}$$

The value i represents the complexity and risk vector.

Fuzzy-AHP Process Determining and prioritizing critical complexity-driven risk factors is important in order to recommend any practicable decision. Risk assessment methods such as AHP, VIKOR, PROMETHE, TOPSIS, ELECTRE among others have been applied for multi-criteria decision making (MCDM), particularly in relation to the assessment of risk criteria (C.-W. Chang, 2014; Islam et al., 2017; Li et al., 2013). The use of AHP for assessing criterion weighting has become popular in the construction risk management field (Li et al., 2013). Saaty (Saaty, 2003) has introduced AHP to develop a hierarchical structure of related criteria for decisions.

Many researchers have developed a Fuzzy-AHP technique for solving MCDM related problems particularly in construction risk management (Russo & Camanho, 2015). This MCDM process includes fuzzy numbers as elements in the pair-wise comparison matrix to replace linguistic or crisp values. Buckley (Buckley, 1985) has introduced this direct-approach of fuzzy weights to calculate the eigenvectors of the matrix. Chang (D. Y. Chang, 1996) has also presented an extensive analytic approach for finding fuzzy-based eigenvectors (λ -max) using a fuzzy triangular membership function. Many studies have followed this extent analysis approach in fuzzy-AHP for solving MCDM related problems (Prascevic & Prascevic, 2017; Samantra et al., 2017; Taylan et al., 2014).

The ranking algorithm of a direct-approach comprising of AHP with extent analysis of fuzzy weights has been adopted here to calculate the degree of risk using Equations 2-5. In this process, for n risk criteria, a matrix $X = x_{ij}$ (see Equation 6) has been computed, where x_{ij} is the value of i th-criterion of risk with respect to j th-criterion, $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. A weight vector W for the decision matrix has been expressed as $[w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n]$, where $W_j \in \mathfrak{R}$ is a weight vector of criterion C_j and $w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_n = 1$.

$$X = (x_{ij}) = \begin{matrix} & \begin{matrix} C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_n \end{matrix} \\ \begin{matrix} C_{11} \\ C_{21} \\ \vdots \\ C_{m1} \end{matrix} & \begin{bmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \dots & \ddots & \vdots \\ x_{m1} & x_{m2} & \dots & x_{mn} \end{bmatrix} \end{matrix} \tag{6}$$

Priority weight vectors of x_{ij} have been transformed into a fuzzified comparison matrix to get a fuzzified weighted matrix, such that \tilde{a}_{ij} represents a fuzzified decision matrix of risk elements for both the likelihood and the magnitude of the risk factor. Next, fuzzy synthetic extent values are computed from the fuzzified pair-wise comparison matrices using Equation 7 as presented by (Buckley, 1985). A weight vector called center of area, has been computed by normalizing the non-fuzzified weight vectors using Equation 8. Finally, rankings of each criterion according to the risk severity, have been generated by exploring the concept of RII, suggested by (Hossen et al., 2015) and (Taylan et al., 2014), as shown in Equation 9.

$$\text{Fuzzy synthetic extent} = S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{x}_{ij} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \tilde{x}_{ij} \right]^{-1} \tag{7}$$

$$\text{Centre of Area (COA)} = w_i = \left(\frac{a+b+c+d}{4} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Relative Importance index (RII)} = \sqrt{\text{FN}_i \text{LO} \times \text{FN}_i \text{MO}} \quad (9)$$

Methodology: Procedural Steps

This section describes the steps taken to develop a hybrid method based on fuzzy-AHP for constructing a risk breakdown structure and developing a cost-risk contingency model for metropolitan construction projects. The database used for this research [needs reference] is an anonymous database of expert's subjective judgments, developed through a focus group study of ten construction executives and managers, who have been actively associated with construction projects (Samantra et al., 2017). Subjective evaluations related to cost overrun were recorded in three rounds for this database. In the first round, data was collected for developing the hierarchical breakdown structure of potential risk factors for cost overrun on a binary scale. In the second round, a linguistic scale is used to record the risk response using a pair-comparison scale. In the last round, data related to project cost overrun were collected for each identified risk factor for cost analysis.

During the focus group process, experts were requested to record their judgments. After getting an aggregate response on a binary scale, a structured framework of risk factors had been constructed. Next, a questionnaire based on a pair-comparison scale (using super-decision software) was developed and distributed amongst the experts to record risk related information, also considering complex risk interactions (Taillandier et al., 2015). Altogether, twenty project risk factors were included in the structured questionnaire. For each factor the likelihood of occurrence and magnitude of impact were measured on a seven points' linguistic scale (Fang & Marle, 2012; Khodakarami & Abdi, 2014; Liu et al., 2016).

Identification of Risk Breakdown Structure

Based on literature, different complexity-driven risk factors were transformed into a binary state of 'True (T)' or 'False (F)' for selection during the focus group study (Qazi et al., 2016). Afterwards, the experts' aggregate opinion was obtained and a breakdown of critical risk factors was constructed for the prioritization process. Tables 1 presents the twenty risk factors classified into different sources such as: (1) the engineering design process; (2) construction management practices; (3) construction safety standards; (4) geographical natural hazards; and (5) domestic social and economic problems, as defined by (Samantra et al., 2017).

Table 1. List of risk factors for cost overrun in metropolitan construction projects.

Risk dimensions	ID	Risk factors under specific dimensions	Source (s)
Engineering design process (D1)	PD1	Inappropriate designing process	Dikmen et al.(Dikmen et al., 2010); Eisenhardt and Graebner (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007)
	DE2	Design drawing faults	Jato-Espino et al.(Jato-Espino et al., 2014)
	IW3	Inconsistency in work flow	Doloi et al.(Doloi et al., 2012)
	SI4	Poor site inspection	Terstegen et al.(Terstegen et al., 2016); Cho and Eppinger(Cho & Eppinger, 2005)
Construction management practices (D2)	CP5	Poor construction planning	Dikmen et al.(Dikmen et al., 2010)
	ES6	Insufficient skill	Lazzerini and Mkrtyan(Lazzerini & Mkrtyan, 2011)Budayan et al.(Budayan et al., 2018)
	DF7	Delay in transferring facilities	Boateng et al.(Boateng et al., 2015)
	SM8	Unstable supply of materials	Zhang et al.(Zhang et al., 2016)
Construction safety standard (D3)	PI9	Inadequate protection of infrastructure	Tahir et al.(Tahir et al., 2011); Shafiee(Shafiee, 2015)
	SP10	Inadequate safety procedures	Eybpoosh et al. (Eybpooosh et al., 2011); Camós et al.(Camós et al., 2016)
	PE11	Ineffective protection of the environment	Satiennam et al.(Satiennam et al., 2006)
Geographical natural hazards (D4)	TC12	Mismanagement of traffic control	Wang et al.(Wang et al., 2016)
	HR13	Heavy rainfall	Wang et al.(Wang et al., 2016)
	SC14	Super cyclonic storm	Chang(C.-W. Chang, 2014)
	EQ15	Earthquake	Samantra et al.(Samantra et al., 2017)
	WS16	Ground water seepage	Boateng et al. (Boateng et al., 2015); Valipour et al. (Valipour et al., 2015)

		al., 2015)	
Domestic social and economic problems (D5)	PI17	Political intervention	Senouci et al.(Senouci et al., 2016); Fazekas and Tóth(Fazekas & Tóth, 2018)
	PM18	Increases in prices of construction materials	Eybpoosh et al.(Eyboosh et al., 2011); Doloi et al. 2012(Doloi et al., 2012)
	WS19	Increases in workers' salaries	Tsavdaroglou et al.(Tsavdaroglou et al., 2018)
	NR20	Protest of residents	Eybpoosh et al.(Eyboosh et al., 2011)

Linguistic Scales and Fuzzy Membership Function

To effectively assess the subjective judgments of the experts, a linguistic scale was designed to measure the semantic strength of an event, as suggested by (Rezakhani et al., 2014) and (Samantra et al., 2017). In addition, fuzzy numbers were used to represent a set of linguistic measurement values for each property of the risk event (Fouladgar et al., 2012; Zhang et al., 2017). In this work, the likelihood and magnitude for risk events have been quantified by using linguistic scales of seven attributes (Samantra et al., 2017) with a corresponding trapezoidal fuzzy membership function (Prascevic & Prascevic, 2017), see Table 2.

Table 2.Fuzzy linguistic scale for assessing the likelihood and magnitude of risk event.

Linguistic scale	Description	Crisp values	Fuzzy membership function ($\delta_F(Z)$)	Fuzzy membership function	Reciprocal fuzzy number
Very rare (VR)	possibility of occurrence is negligible	1	$LVL = \tilde{F}(VRL, VRM, VRN, VRU)$	(1, 1, 1.5, 2)	(1/2, 1/1.5, 1, 1)
Rare (R)	possible to occur an event	2	$LR = \tilde{F}(RL, RM, RN, RU)$	(1, 1.5, 2.5, 3)	(1/3, 1/2.5, 1/1.5, 1)
Occasional (O)	Likely to occur an event	3	$LO = \tilde{F}(OL, OM, ON, OU)$	(2, 2.5, 3.5, 4)	(1/4, 1/3.5, 1/2.5, 1/2)
Probable (P)	Likely to occur an event several times	4	$LP = \tilde{F}(PL, PM, PN, PU)$	(3, 3.5, 4.5, 5)	(1/5, 1/4.5, 1/3.5, 1/3)
Frequent (F)	Likely to occur an event frequently	5	$LF = \tilde{F}(FL, FM, FN, FU)$	(4, 4.5, 5.5, 6)	(1/6, 1/5.5, 1/4.5, 1/4)
Very frequent (VF)	Much frequent to occur an event	6	$LVF = \tilde{F}(VFL, VFM, VFN, VFU)$	(5, 5.5, 6.5, 7)	(1/7, 1/6.5, 1/5.5, 1/5)
Absolutely certain (AC)	Expected to occur an event with absolute certainty	7	$LAC = \tilde{F}(ACL, ACM, ACN, ACU)$	(6, 6.5, 7.5, 8)	(1/8, 1/7.5, 1/6.5, 1/6)

Note: Fuzzy trapezoidal distributions against crisp values are calculated as follows: $x-1, x-.5, x+.5, x+1$

Empirical Case

In order to evaluate the cost-risk contingency framework, a case study was conducted using the data from the first Orange Line Metro Train (OLMT) project in the city of Lahore in Pakistan. Foreseeing the economic potential of growing metro services in Lahore, large investments have already been made under the China Pakistan concession agreement, such as the One Belt One Road initiative to develop and expand the facilities in the future. The initial project cost was estimated to be US\$ 1,626 million for the length of the total track. Later, the cost of the project escalated to around US\$1,900million. The OLMT project (one of the most expensive infrastructure projects in Pakistan) is experiencing cost overrun issues due to its complex structure and the impact of different types of risk factors.

The Lahore OLMT project started in 2014 and was expected to be completed during 2019. Out of the total 27.1km long track, 25.4 km is above the ground, while rest of the track is underground. The total number of station sites is 36, while its total passenger capacity is expected to reach 250,000 passengers daily. The train has a nominal capacity of 1,300 passengers, seated in seven cars. The average speed of the train is 45 km/h (28 mph)(Tribune, 2014).

This project had many ongoing issues which caused cost overruns and generated a chaotic situation. Some of the major problems faced during the project were the use of technology, financing, mass mobility of the public, and health and safety. It is hoped that the outcome of this research may help the project managers to understand the risks associated with the project and to put in place appropriate action plans to eliminate (or reduce) the severity of the impact of these risks.

Database and Paired-Comparison Matrix

The database includes linguistic data on the likelihood and magnitude of each identified risk was obtained from experts during the focus group study. During the judgment process for this, the decision makers were asked to provide their judgments on a pair-comparison scale (Khodakarami & Abdi, 2014). Subsequently, the decision makers were requested to give a fair aggregate opinion after deliberate discussion, but not to share their individual opinion to evade bias in judgments. It is worth mentioning that after prioritizing risk factors related to cost overruns, the experts were requested to record cost variations against each element of complexity-driven risk factors for further cost analysis.

Pair-comparison addresses the states of n risk factors (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n) with m dimensions (D_1, D_2, \dots, D_m) by g experts H_g . In a risk matrix, $x_{ij}(i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ is specified separately for both states comparing the likelihood and magnitude of the risks i.e., R_i criterion over that of R_j criterion respectively. The values of x_{ij} represent the weight (ω) vector of the likelihood and magnitude in accordance with the comparison of R_i with R_j by the decision makers.

During the pair-comparison process, the consistency strength was checked using the consistency ratio $CR = CI/RI$, as suggested by (Saaty, 2003). For this work, the CR values of the priority comparison matrices of likelihood and magnitude corresponding to risk events are 0.085 and 0.077 respectively. Next, the information in the form of un weighted matrices was transformed into fuzzy scales (as shown in Table 2) for further extent analysis.

4.2. Computation of Risk Ranking

The ranking algorithm of fuzzy-AHP characterizes important risk events against their level of severity. After the de-fuzzification process, the relative weight vector RII is computed separately for each risk event of matrix \tilde{a}_{ij} considering both likelihood and magnitude. Individual rankings of complexity-driven risk factors were computed in accordance with the center of area for likelihood and magnitude separately using Equation 8. Subsequently, a combined effect of likelihood and magnitude for risk severity was computed and ranked using Equation 9. It was found that the risk factors like ‘poor construction plan’, ‘unstable supply of construction materials’ and ‘prices of construction materials’ possess high individual risk ratings in determining the overall risk scores. Table 3 shows the scores of the relative importance index, indicating the severity level of each risk factor in relation to cost overrun.

The percentage (%) contribution of each risk dimension relative to the overall risk level was also calculated. It was found that the construction management dimension D_2 contributes to the overall risk with a rating value of 28%. The risk dimension ‘engineering design’ has the second highest percentage contribution to the overall construction of risk level. The risk dimension ‘construction safety-related’ was found to contribute the least with a risk value of 10.70%.

Cost Analysis

The importance of this cost-risk analysis is to validate the cost-risk contingency model presented in section 2 which identifies the level of additional cost required to manage project progress in response to the risk factors. It is obvious that a risk factor may occur several times over a project life cycle, leading to some variation in the risk consequences. In addition to this, project cost related decisions also vary during the project. Therefore, risk and cost related results are re-evaluated by generating a large number of iterations for each cost-risk scenario.

The significance of the study is to explore the key complexity-driven risks factors for cost overrun problems and estimate the additional cost required to manage the response to each identified risk factor. Expected amount of cost variation for each identified risk was recorded for each expert. Obviously risk scores may vary for different experts. In addition to this, project cost related decisions are also dependent on the expert’s attitude. Therefore, this study has further attempted to analyze the cost overrun while considering the impact of risk scores according to the experts’ different risk-bearing attitudes, for example pessimistic ($\alpha = 0.5$), neutral ($\alpha = 0.5$), and optimistic ($\alpha = 0.5$).

Table 3. Ranking of risk factors using fuzzified pair-wise comparison matrix.

D i	Ri	Risk LO	Risk MI	FNiL O	FNi MI	FNiLO× FNiMI	RII	Ranki ng order	Risk percentage
	R0 1	1.37, 1.63, 2.21, 2.58	1.10, 1.34, 1.98, 2.45	0.037	0.08	0.0031	0.06	07	0.265 (26.5%)
D 1	R0 2	1.38, 1.72, 2.44, 2.89	0.96, 1.09, 1.53, 1.81	0.091	0.03	0.0034	0.06	06	
	R0 3	0.86, 1.08, 1.55, 1.87	1.29, 1.55, 2.28, 2.76	0.066	0.06	0.0041	0.07	04	0.278
	R0 4	1.12, 1.41, 2.04, 2.45	0.97, 1.14, 1.69, 2.08	0.027	0.09	0.0026	0.05	08	
	R0 5	1.22, 1.50, 2.08, 2.45	0.83, 1.03, 1.54, 1.93	0.050	0.08	0.0041	0.07	03	

D 2	R0 6	1.81, 2.12, 2.79, 3.16	0.55, 0.68, 1.02, 1.29	0.067	0.05	0.0038	0.07	05	(27.8%)
	R0 7	0.61, 0.77, 1.13, 1.38	1.28, 1.58, 2.33, 2.81	0.146	0.01	0.0023	0.05	10	
	R0 8	0.52, 0.59, 0.81, 0.98	1.58, 1.88, 2.71, 3.18	0.079	0.05	0.0044	0.07	02	
D 3	R0 9	0.60, 0.71, 0.98, 1.20	1.26, 1.49, 2.19, 2.67	0.009	0.02	0.0003	0.01	20	0.107 (10.7%)
	R1 0	3.06, 3.52, 4.44, 4.94	0.26, 0.30, 0.42, 0.52	0.014	0.05	0.0007	0.03	15	
	R1 1	0.58, 0.66, 0.86, 1.01	1.35, 1.55, 2.18, 2.58	0.026	0.02	0.0007	0.03	16	
D 4	R1 2	0.33, 0.38, 0.53, 0.65	0.87, 1.07, 1.64, 2.03	0.020	0.03	0.0006	0.02	17	0.149 (14.9%)
	R1 3	0.62, 0.77, 1.11, 1.34	0.45, 0.53, 0.75, 0.93	0.029	0.07	0.0023	0.05	11	
	R1 4	0.64, 0.77, 1.10, 1.36	0.33, 0.38, 0.55, 0.70	0.130	0.00	0.0003	0.01	19	
D 5	R1 5	0.28, 0.32, 0.44, 0.52	0.79, 0.96, 1.40, 1.68	0.036	0.02	0.0010	0.03	13	0.201 (20.1%)
	R1 6	0.46, 0.56, 0.80, 0.97	0.38, 0.45, 0.67, 0.85	0.018	0.05	0.0011	0.03	12	
	R1 7	0.40, 0.45, 0.60, 0.72	0.48, 0.55, 0.80, 1.00	0.032	0.07	0.0025	0.05	09	
D 5	R1 8	0.27, 0.32, 0.44, 0.55	0.56, 0.69, 1.02, 1.25	0.072	0.07	0.0052	0.08	01	0.201 (20.1%)
	R1 9	2.59, 3.06, 4.00, 4.49	0.35, 0.00, 0.00, 0.00	0.015	0.03	0.0006	0.02	18	
	R2 0	0.20, 0.22, 0.28, 0.32	0.46, 0.53, 0.75, 0.94	0.036	0.02	0.0008	0.03	14	

Note: Di= risk dimensions; FNiLO = normalized values of the fuzzified likelihood of occurrence; FNiMI = normalized values of fuzzified magnitude of impact. A moderate level $\alpha = 0.5$ risk score against cost variation was selected for relative decision making using a three-point estimation approach (Saputra & Latiffianti, 2015). It has been noted that the maximum projected cost was taken for the control of ‘unstable supply of material’ and managing the ‘increase in prices of construction materials’. The ‘changes in project design’ and ‘poor planning’ have also created cost overrun issues for the described metropolitan transit project. Figure 1 shows the simulated values of cost variation incurred to control specific risk scenario. Table 4 describes cost-risk contingency values generated through the simulated score of each risk factor along with the associated simulated cost required to mitigate that risk.

Figure 1. Simulated results of cost variation for managing critical risk factors.

The results obtained from a cost-risk analysis can be used for planning the cost-risk contingency. This contingency model determines the additional cost required to mitigate the risk impact in order to complete the

project on time rather than to terminate it before completion. This model also emphasizes that the cost of each risk event should be considered separately along with the estimation of the baseline cost particularly for metropolitan projects particularly in developing countries.

Study Findings and Implications

Fuzzy-AHP has been widely adopted to solve real-world problems. Such methods effectively address complex decision-making problems without the formal language used to explicate their occurrence (Love et al., 2016). A structured cost-risk contingency model for cost overrun was developed for a metropolitan transit project, using fuzzy-AHP based on a combination of judgments and data.

An empirical study on the important issue of cost overrun and its potential control measures of a metropolitan rapid transit project in Pakistan has been presented. The study has assessed complexity-driven risk factors by considering twenty risk factors from different endogenous and exogenous sources such as technical, managerial and environmental issues (Fang & Marle, 2012; Flyvbjerg et al., 2004; Liu et al., 2016; Samantra et al., 2017). In addition, in order to develop the cost-risk contingency model, a cost-risk analysis has been performed to measure the sensitivity of cost variation against each identified risk.

It was observed that the cost variation appears to be highly sensitive to the dimension 'construction management'. As far as individual ratings of identified risk factors are concerned, 'unstable supply of critical construction materials', 'managing the sudden increase in material prices', 'changes in project design' and 'poor construction planning' appear to be the most significant factors creating vulnerability to cost overrun problems for the metropolitan transit project. These key risk factors should be considered for developing cost related contingency plans in the future.

Table 4. Simulated results of cost-risk analysis against three point's distribution of each risk scores.

D i	Risk Factors	Ri	Pessimist ic (P)		Most likely (M)		Optimisti c (O)		Re-evaluated simulation results			
			Ri sk α = 0	Co st α = 0	Ris k α = 0.5	Co st α = 0.5	Ri sk α = 1	Co st α = 1	Simul ated risk value	Simul ated cost value	Ris k SD	Co st SD
D 1	Inappropriate project designing process	PD 1	0.0 4	4.9 5	0.0 65	6.6 6	0.0 00	8.4 00	0.06	6.659	0.0 03	0.5 75
		DE 2	0.0 5	5.5 0	0.0 67	6.8 8	0.0 00	8.5 00	0.067	6.824	0.0 05	0.5 00
	Design drawing faults	IW 3	0.0 5	5.6 25	0.0 74	7.5 7	0.0 00	8.6 00	0.069	7.347	0.0 03	0.4 96
		SI4	0.0 4	2 59	0.0 59	2.5 8	0.0 30	3.1 30	0.059	2.506	0.0 07	0.1 88
	Poor site inspection	CP 5	0.0 5	6.5 0	0.0 74	8.2 8	0.0 25	10. 25	0.071	8.219	0.0 05	0.6 25
		ES6	0.0 5	5.5 0	0.0 71	6.2 8	0.0 50	7.7 50	0.069	6.319	0.0 05	0.3 75
D 2	Insufficient skill in construction	DF 7	0.0 4	2.8 0	0.0 56	3.5 4	0.0 75	4.3 75	0.051	3.510	0 0	0.2 63
		SM 8	0.0 5	6.7 5	0.0 77	9 7	0.0 50	11. 50	0.071	9.039	0.0 03	0.7 92
	Unstable supply of materials	PI9	0.0 1	0.3 75	0.0 18	0.5 4	0.0 0	0.7 0	0.02	0.479	0.0 05	0.0 54
D 3	Inadequate protection of nearby infrastructure	SP1 0	0.0 2	0.1 8	0.0 31	0.2 4	0.0 4	0.2 80	0.031	0.236	0.0 03	0.0 17
		PE1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.03	0.100	0.0	0.0

	environment	1	2	75	3	4	25			03	08	
	Mismanagement of traffic control	TC	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.034	0.298	0.0	0.0
		12	2	25	28	7	80			08	26	
	Heavy rainfall	HR	0.0	1.8	0.0	2.5	0.0	3.2	0.05	2.507	0	0.2
		13	4	75	55	4	00				21	
D	Super cyclonic storm	SC	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.021	0.100	0.0	0.0
		14	2	75	19	3	25			02	08	
4	Earthquake	EQ	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.3	0.04	0.211	0.0	0.0
		15	3	50	37	6	50			05	33	
	Ground water seepage	WS	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.6	0.0	0.7	0.034	0.611	0.0	0.0
		16	2	0	38	3	50			02	42	
	Political intervention	PI1	0.0	3.8	0.0	4.5	0.0	5.6	0.054	4.556	0.0	0.3
		7	3	0	58	6	25			05	04	
	Increases in prices construction materials	PM	0.0	7.5	0.0	10	0.0	12	0.076	9.896	0.0	0.7
D		18	5	0	83	7				03	50	
5	Increases in workers' salaries	WS	0.0	1.8	0.0	2.5	0.0	3	0.036	2.464	0.0	0.1
		19	2	75	27	9				12	88	
	Protest of residents	NR	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.028	0.102	0	0.0
		20	2	75	32	2	3				09	

Note: Di= risk dimensions; FNiLO = normalized values of the fuzzified likelihood of occurrence; FNiMI = normalized values of fuzzified magnitude of impact. All given cost values are in an amount of million dollar, SD = standard deviation; for expected value computation, three points estimation = $(p+4m+o)/6$.

The current work has contributed to developing a cost-risk contingency model for metropolitan infrastructure projects by articulating an efficient integrated approach of fuzzy logic and AHP. This study contributes by providing a practical technique to evaluate the risks and estimate cost overrun in construction using through three simple steps: (1) developing a structured hierarchical breakdown structure of potential complexity-risk factors in transit projects (see Table 1); (2) calculating the severity of the risk for each identified risk factor under high uncertainty by using a fuzzy-AHP process; and (3) performing a cost analysis for cost re-evaluation and developing a cost-risk contingency plan using an effective integrated approach of Fuzzy-AHP and MCS.

From a practical point of view, this work introduces a decision making tool that permits construction experts and other engineering related project managers: (1) to have an overview of the most frequent and critical causes of cost overrun in metropolitan infrastructure projects; (2) to use a cost-risk contingency model for future risk management and maintaining stability in budgeting. The chosen risk analysis process for the construction project may provide multiple benefits to managers: (1) to consider the required technical capabilities in construction; (2) to allocate funds effectively in the planning stage while considering the critical associated risks; and (3) to identify risks at an early stage which could improve the project delivery process and help to complete the project within the predetermined budget. Furthermore, this procedure may be used by experts from other engineering domains by replacing the complexity-risk factors with the relevant ones for their field.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to redress the prevalent cost overruns being experienced by mega-construction projects under high uncertainty. Aiming to solve cost overrun problems in metropolitan infrastructure projects and facilitate decision making for effective budgeting in the future, a cost-risk contingency model was developed using fuzzy logic and AHP. Using Fuzzy-AHP, a hierarchical breakdown structure of risk factors at different levels of relative importance was designed. The study used experts' tolerance level like optimistic, neutral and pessimistic as risk input values for measuring the expected cost variation against each identified risk factor. Furthermore, in order to develop the cost-risk contingency framework, risk and cost related results were-evaluated by generating large number of iterations in MCS for each cost-risk scenario. While exploring the significance of critical risk factors for cost overruns, important risk factors such as 'inappropriate design and poor engineering', 'increase in the price of construction material' and 'delay in transferring existing facilities' were identified. Additional budgeted costs would be required for mitigating and controlling these risks in order to successfully achieve the project progress and maintain stability in budgeting.

The study has investigated the expected additional cost required to mitigate the risk consequences for particular project activities and developed a cost-risk contingency to address the cost planning in the future. This model helps in the effective calculation of total construction cost while considering tentative mitigating cost required against each risk impact. The study has proposed a practical approach to address the common issue of project cost overrun problems in developing countries. The proposed contingency model may be adapted to prevent cost overrun issues in other engineering management related domains. To employ the risk analysis framework in the context of a specific problem, knowledge and a clear understanding of probable risks are required.

Fuzzy logic has been combined with AHP for comparative ranking matrices. This integrated approach does not consider the interdependencies between complexity and complexity-driven risk factors in a structured hierarchy as recommended by (Qazi et al., 2016). This study could be extended to apply an integrated approach of fuzzy and Bayesian inference for effective ranking of interdependent risk factors (Islam et al., 2017). Finally, this study adds value to the existing body of knowledge by providing a cost-risk contingency framework to evaluate the complexity-driven risk factors in related to cost overrun problems in metropolitan transit projects. The findings could provide additional strategic support for continuing or future projects.

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Author Information

Maqsood Zia Ahmed Shah

Shah Abdul Latif University,
Department of Statistics

Sirajud Din

Assistant Professor,
Department of Management Sciences,
Khushal Khan Khattak University Karak

Mumtaz Ali Junejo

Shah Abdul Latif University
Institute of Commerce

Fawwad Mahmood Butt

ILMA University Karachi
Department of Business Administration

Imran Ahmed Shah

ILMA University Karachi
Department of Business Administration

Mansoor Ahmed Junejo

Name of Institution or University
IBA Sukkur, Doctoral student, University of
Jyvaskyla School of Business and Economics

Saaherah Basil Alkilany

Hospitality and Event Management Lead Lecturer,
LTUC (Luminus Technical University College

Ghulam Akbar Ali Khaskeli

Shah Abdul Latif University
Institute of Commerce
